

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

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California State University, Long Beach
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TELEMEDICINE-BASED GUIDELINE DEVELOPMENT FOR
HEADACHE PATIENTS IN AN OUTPATIENT CLINIC

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

Established patients of an outpatient neurology clinic who request same-day evaluations for headache exacerbations may be debilitated from attending an in-person appointment. Current evidence from a literature review showed that telemedicine is a feasible solution for patients to gain same-day access to their neurology providers and reduce the burden of physically attending medical appointments. This project developed a guideline to assess patient readiness for telemedicine. Additionally, the project also produced a telemedicine appointment algorithm and patient education material that headache-sufferers can use to determine what symptoms can be managed independently, addressed with telemedicine, or required immediate emergency care.

Keywords: telemedicine, headache, migraines, appointment algorithm, education

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Background

According to the World Health Organization (2016), headache is a common neurologic ailment that affects 50% of adults aged 18-65 years worldwide. Headaches are classified as primary or secondary disorders according to their etiology. Primary headache disorders include migraine and tension-type headaches (Muller, Alstadhaug, & Bekkelund, 2016). Secondary headache disorders are mainly due to medication overuse (Bekkelund & Muller, 2019), but may also be due to infection or trauma (Rizzoli & Mullally, 2018). The Global Burden of Disease Study measured headaches as the second-highest contributor of years lived with disability (Saylor & Steiner, 2018). Headache disorders inflict a multi-faceted burden on an individual's quality of life, finances, employment, and overall health (Friedman, Rajan, & Seidmann, 2019). As a widely misunderstood condition, misdiagnosed and mismanaged headaches by non-headache specialists led to disability in 68-77% of Americans (Lipton et al., 2003).

A narrative review of 49 studies that spanned 25 years by Leonardi and Raggi (2019) summarized how headaches impact work, school, quality of life, and finances. First, patients who suffered migraines missed between 3.2 and 89.2 workdays per year. Second, children with migraines missed an average of 4.1 school days per year, which consequently involved lost workdays by their caregivers as well. Third, the review measured a higher interictal burden, which encompassed less time spent being active, higher fatigue, and lower stamina (Leonardi & Raggi, 2019). Finally, patients spent on average \$2649 per year to manage episodic migraines and \$8243 per year to cope with chronic migraines, in which 60-64% is allocated to direct medical expenses (Leonardi & Raggi, 2019).

In the United States and Canada, there are fewer than 600 certified headache specialists (Friedman et al., 2019). Due to the limited availability of these specialists, there is a need for

access to care for both acute and chronic treatment of headache disorders. Currently, proper diagnosis and optimal management of headaches require routine office visits that are collectively costly. Patients struggling with a debilitating headache may be physically and mentally incapacitated from safely completing routine tasks, such as commuting. These patients may unavoidably reschedule their appointment, which delays their care. This vulnerable population ultimately compromises either their medical or personal well-being at the expense of inaccessibility to headache specialists.

Telehealth is an innovative health care system that integrates technology to facilitate remote communication, data monitoring, and patient education (Dorsey et al., 2018). A concentration of telehealth that provides clinical care services to the patient is called telemedicine, which is a feasible solution to increase access to neurology providers and reduce the burden of physically attending medical appointments. Authors suggest this modality is equally as effective as the traditional face-to-face visit (Bekkelund & Muller, 2019; Muller et al., 2017). In addition to the primary goal of reducing wait-times to see a provider, other telemedicine strengths include cost-savings of travel, parking, and lost wages (Bekkelund & Muller, 2019; Muller, Alstadhaug & Bekkelund, 2016).

Problem Statement

An outpatient neurology clinic in Southern California treats various neurologic syndromes, many of which are headache disorders. According to Rizzoli and Mullaly (2018), more than 90% of patients with headache complaints are due to a non-acute primary headache disorder. Although this is a reassuring statistic, patients experiencing severe headaches, who then request a same-day, in-office evaluation may not be physically or mentally capable to drive to the appointment. Therefore, without the advancement of telemedicine, patients who feel they

need prompt care are re-directed to the emergency department (ED), where they receive temporary relief. These brief treatments can contribute to secondary headaches caused by, for example, medication overuse. Medication overuse is defined as frequent intake of acute analgesics, including both over-the-counter (OTC) medications and prescribed opioids, which consequently leads to symptoms of analgesic dependency (Vandenbussche et al., 2018).

Ultimately, the creation of an alternative approach to the traditional in-person visit provides safe and convenient access to treat headache disorders and decrease associated burdens.

Although patients first attend an in-person consultation for a complete neurologic evaluation with a physical exam to rule out acute secondary causes, the follow-up visits can be completed using HIPAA compliant web-based videoconferencing programs such as Zoom or Doxy.me. This software allows patients to complete the visit in the comfort of their own homes, especially during a disabling headache that may impair driving. Additionally, the author is the only provider present in the office with the most availability, and therefore, readily able to fulfill same-day telemedicine needs. Furthermore, telemedicine is gradually becoming an included service covered by both private and public insurances. As a result, this alternative not only benefits the patient with lower copays, but also maintains equivalent reimbursement rates for the practice (Patel et al., 2019).

Purpose Statement

The purpose of this Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) project is to develop a telemedicine-based, primary headache management guideline for patients to gain same-day access to neurology providers and reduce the burden of physically attending office appointments.

The project will be executed with the following objectives:

Objectives

1. Recruit 20 participants to assess headache disability, lifestyle behaviors, and perception of telemedicine in the author's neurology practice.
2. Develop and pilot an appointment algorithm based on best evidence for non-clinical staff to properly triage patients for telemedicine.
3. Develop and distribute educational material regarding headache self-management and utilization of telemedicine.

Supporting Framework

Kurt Lewin's Change Theory is rooted in social psychology and provides an operational framework for planned change applicable to nursing informatics (Kaminski, 2011; Nelson, 2002; Schultz, 2010) (Appendix A). The model is comprised of three phases based on fostering forces of change while limiting resistors of change: unfreeze, change, and refreeze (Schultz, 2010). Applying Lewin's Change Theory will highlight the need for restructuring the appointment system, motivating neurologists and staff participation, addressing patients' needs using a technologically advanced set-up, and stabilizing the changes as new standards of care. The nurse practitioner is the change agent leading the movement through each phase.

Unfreeze

The unfreezing phase consists of recognizing the need for change, gathering leadership support, motivating key players to desire change, and acknowledging concerns (Kaminski, 2011).

First, determine the need for change. The clinic's all-inclusive waiting list is a clear indication of high demand and limited availability. If the practice is not able to promptly address complaints, the appropriate treatments are delayed. The author focused on primary headache

disorders because most symptoms can be managed remotely (Rizzoli & Mullaly, 2018). Therefore, assessing the headache population's characteristics (such as the frequency of ED visits for acute headaches) will yield baseline data that supports the need for telemedicine to increase access to care. Creating an algorithm to triage acute headaches of established patients into telemedicine can help shorten wait-times. Additionally, telemedicine may be appealing to stable headache patients scheduled for routine visits or medication refills because of the convenience. Therefore, a handout regarding headache care enhanced by telemedicine will attract attention from non-urgent patients.

Second, draw leadership interests and backing. Presenting the supervising physicians, who are also the practice owners, with the headache patient assessment data will justify the use of telemedicine. Key findings in the literature, such as an increase in access to care and comparable reimbursement and patient satisfaction, will garner their support from a business and clinical standpoint. As the change agent piloting this protocol, the nurse practitioner will encourage and support telemedicine adoption by the other neurologists, which will eventually expand this feature efficiently to all headache patients in the clinic. Third, as front-line communicators, the neurologists will be initiators while the office staff will be enforcers of the protocol. Therefore, involving fellow neurologists and office staff in developing the algorithm collectively will increase buy-in and allow for transparency in the process. The unfreezing phase accents the disadvantages of the current scheduling model, encourages the advantages of a new protocol, and prepares for subsequent resistance to facilitate change.

Change

The changing phase involves constant communication, easing conflict, and empowering those involved in the process to agree to change and act (Kaminski, 2011). Nelson (2006) states

that this phase is unstable and anxiety levels tend to rise. Therefore, tailoring specific approaches to each group of participants will ensure successful implementation.

Neurologists

There are five physicians in the practice, three of whom are already members of a large telemedicine organization that provides inpatient acute stroke consultations. The physicians with tele-neurology experience should more readily accept and use telemedicine in an outpatient setting. The two remaining neurologists, however, may be hesitant to learn a new system of patient care. A provider-only meeting in which experienced users share feedback and offer suggestions regarding telemedicine utilization will ease anxiety.

Office Staff

As operators of the new appointment algorithm, gaining office staff participation is critical. Understandably, the staff is already overwhelmed with their own designated responsibilities and asking them to incorporate new tasks can be met with heavy resistance. Thus, there will be weekly staff and provider meetings to communally develop and modify the appointment algorithm. Nelson (2006) also advises that the change agent must anticipate and minimize actions of resistance, including missed meetings, failure to provide feedback, or refusing to adopt the change properly or entirely. Stress-reducing tactics that may encourage and empower staff include providing food at meetings or offering rewards or recognition for early adopters of change. Kaminski (2011) measures accomplishment of the change phase by participant acceptance and joining the momentum to bring it into action. When staff can navigate the algorithm comfortably and schedule appointments appropriate to the acuity level, then the protocol is successful.

Patients

An educational flyer will present brief headache facts, simple self-care recommendations and resources, symptoms appropriate for telemedicine, and basic telemedicine features. The overarching theme of the flyer will be centered on patient-empowerment, essentially guiding the patient towards various self-directed treatments, and if help is needed, how telemedicine will ease accessibility. This change may initially generate high traffic calls and correspondences among anxious patients who may not be willing to lose the physical presence of their provider. However, responding to them promptly will reflect how personal connection can remain consistent. Patients who persistently decline virtual visits or refuse to adopt headache-care habits may book the next appointment in-person, and the provider can help clarify any concerns. It is crucial to emphasize how telemedicine could provide them savings in time, finances, and increase convenience by providing improved and timely access to their provider. Achieving the change phase at the patient-level will be evident as more established headache sufferers regain their independence and maintain momentum through the use of technology.

Refreeze

The refreezing phase translates to anchoring the change, developing sustainability, and celebrating success (Kaminski, 2011). According to Kaminski (2011), returning to previous habits are easy without a method of reinforcing the new change. Comparable to the changing phase, the continuity of the interventions will be specific to each participant group.

Neurologists and Office Staff

Weekly meetings will be conducted to generate staff feedback and troubleshoot possible problems with the appointment triage guideline, availability of telemedicine appointments allotted per day, and the number of patients agreeing to continue with these virtual visits. The

meetings will keep the protocol at the forefront of the discussion by reviewing specific cases and incorporating recommendations as a team. When the staff readily meets a patient's scheduling needs, patient satisfaction tends to improve, which motivates the staff to continue applying the protocol. Collecting data on the number of virtual visits, headache and lifestyle improvements, and satisfaction with the use of telemedicine will be shared with the neurologists and staff. As the protocol solidifies further, it can be added as part of the office policies and procedures manual. The new standard of care will include refresher training quarterly and be merged into new employee orientation. The nurse practitioner will continue to be the primary change agent and may designate other champion leadership as needed, such as the office manager. Once the protocol is sustainable for at least a year, then those who become change experts are celebrated through recognition (Nelson, 2002). At this phase, the protocol is "frozen" in place and now part of the practice status quo.

Patients

Treatment compliance and headache outcomes will be measured with follow-up surveys, which are similar to the initial assessment. These subsequent surveys will also assess patient satisfaction regarding telemedicine. Any dissatisfied patients may request an in-person opportunity to see a provider and voice their concern. The option to see their provider face-to-face reflects the clinic's ability to deliver continuity of care and noting their complaints can help to improve the overall telemedicine protocol and experience. When patients have appointment modality options and timely access to care using an alternative visit method, they will be more inclined to continue using telemedicine.

Review of Literature

A review of the literature was conducted for the development of a primary headache management guideline. The search utilized electronic databases: PubMed, CINAHL, and Academic Search Premier. The first search for pertinent publications used informatic keywords, such as “telemedicine,” “telehealth,” or “tele-neurology.” The second search encompassed “practice guidelines in adults.” The third search narrowed down “self-management” or “self-care headache treatments.” Each of the three individual searches was paired with clinical symptoms of headache or migraine. Date limitations were set from 2015 to the present to critically analyze more current research. The overall search generated 2614 results. After filtering the studies with the inclusion criteria below, 334 studies remained.

Inclusion criteria limited publications to clinical trials, randomized controlled trials (RCTs), meta-analysis, or systematic reviews from scholarly journals that explored the utilization of telemedicine in headache management among adults 19 years and older. The criteria were refined further to only outpatient settings and the English language. Publications that were pediatric- or adolescent-population based, secondary headache disorders, a flowchart for headache diagnostic and treatment purposes, pharmacologic or device-dependent interventions, or self-managing therapies older than 2015 were excluded. This allowed the focus to be directed towards adult primary headaches, an algorithm that can be used by non-clinical staff to book appointments appropriately and evaluate more current self-directed recommendations. After exclusion criteria was applied, 26 studies remained. To further categorize the studies, there were 17 quantitative, six qualitative, and three mixed-methods studies.

The Use of Telemedicine in Neurology

Two meta-syntheses papers within the last five years thoroughly reviewed tele-neurology subspecialties (Hatcher-Martin et al., 2019) and their various mobile advancements (Dorsey et al., 2018). According to Hatcher-Martin et al. (2019), conditions that generated the most telemedicine studies were dementia and movement disorders. These demonstrate that telemedicine can be utilized for complex neurological disorders. Dorsey et al. (2018) recognized a similar trend in mobile phone applications and wearable sensor studies designed primarily for patients with movement disorders or epilepsy. These advanced mobile technologies can collect objective information such as movement patterns and frequency, which may be difficult to accurately track by the patient or caretakers (Dorsey et al., 2018). Both reviews noted a sparse amount of research dedicated to headaches. However, the headache studies were mostly high-quality RCTs with the potential for generalizability. The RCTs presented positive patient and physician satisfaction, diagnostic accuracy, and improved headache management (Dorsey et al., 2018; Hatcher-Martin et al., 2019). Due to these promising results, the author focused on creating a guideline to implement telemedicine for the clinic's headache patients.

Telemedicine in Non-Acute Headache Management

Five of the seven quantitative studies on telemedicine for non-acute headache disorders were conducted at the University Hospital of Norway by the same three authors (Muller et al., 2016a, 2017a, 2017b, 2017c). They strategically conducted a series of non-inferior RCTs using the same pool of participants, applied reasonable inclusion and exclusion criterium, conducted a one-time neurology consultation either physically or virtually, and analyzed different outcome measures at 3- and 12-month follow-up visits. The outcome measures included patient's acceptance of telemedicine, patient's headache burden, patient's satisfaction, and treatment

efficacy and safety (Muller et al., 2016a, 2017a, 2017b, 2017c). Questionnaires were distributed to collect headache disability data using the Headache Impact Test-6 (HIT-6) and a visual analog scale (VAS). The overall findings showed virtual visits were non-inferior to in-person visits concerning disability, safety, and patient satisfaction (Muller et al., 2016a, 2017a, 2017b, 2017c).

The Norwegian study has strengths and weaknesses. The research strengths included enrollment on a rolling basis. Directly from the referring primary care office, the patients were then randomized into in-person or virtual neurology consult rooms, which were equipped and ready for use (Muller et al., 2016a). As a result, the virtual visit set-up facilitated telemedicine operation. Despite these strengths, there were weaknesses as well. For example, regardless of the visit format, patients were still required to be physically present and they did not have further neurological follow-ups after the initial consult. Unlike other studies that praise telemedicine's ability to complete the visit from any patient location, this was not the case for those patients randomized into telemedicine (Dorsey et al., 2018; Hatcher-Martin et al., 2019).

Although American studies led by Rajan et al. (2017) and Friedman, et al., (2019) had smaller sample sizes, virtual visit participants used telemedicine to its full capacity. First, the initial consults were in-office with the same neurologist, where the patient underwent a full physical exam and then were randomized into either the telemedicine or traditional groups (Rajan et al., 2017; Friedman et al., 2019). Second, patients were emailed a link to pre- and post-visit questionnaires that included a Migraine Disability Assessment Scale (MIDAS) (Rajan et al., 2017; Friedman et al., 2019). Third, the researchers reimbursed the traditional groups for travel and parking expenses to standardize patient costs between groups (Friedman et al., 2019). The strengths of this design allowed for patient-provider rapport to build from a typical consult setting and then continued the specialized care remotely. According to a patient survey, patients

perceived their visit times to be high quality despite a difference in minutes spent (mean of 194 minutes for in-office versus mean of 37 minutes for virtual) (Friedman et al., 2019).

Additionally, telemedicine patients also showed higher adherence to follow-up visits due to convenience (Friedman et al., 2019). Evident weaknesses included exclusion bias among patients refusing the randomization process and the smaller sample sizes. Although the exclusion bias only accounted for five participants during recruitment, this is significant in a sample size of fewer than 20 participants in both groups (Rajan et al., 2017; Friedman et al., 2019).

Triage of Non-Urgent Headaches

This DNP project aims to develop a screening tool for use by non-provider staff to identify appropriate patients for telemedicine. Thus, the literature was searched for tools that could be incorporated into a simple screening algorithm. Unfortunately, most of the published literature presented sophisticated protocols for healthcare workers that included diagnostic, classification, or treatment terms that would exceed the training of the clerical staff who would be utilizing the tools. After careful review, two qualitative reviews summarized *red flag* symptoms that can be translated into telephone screener questions to direct patients appropriately (Becker et al., 2015; Young et al., 2018). Strengths upheld by the articles included the generalizability of the assessment and findings, especially the algorithm flowchart created for primary care providers (Becker et al., 2015). Despite both articles highlighting common urgent headache symptoms, it is not a validated tool. However, it may be sufficient for non-clinical staff to efficiently schedule clinic patients and leave the expanded assessment and plan to the neurology provider.

Non-Pharmaceutical Headache Management

More than 90% of patients with headaches are non-acute and can be managed by the patient (Rizzoli & Mullaly, 2018). Aside from adhering to proper pharmacologic use, there are numerous modalities considered to be self-management or self-care approaches that are behavior-based, non-pharmacologic interventions for chronic conditions (Probyn et al., 2017; Patel et al., 2019; Nichols et al., 2019; White et al., 2019). The literature on self-management methods is driven to motivate and empower individuals to manage their care (Probyn et al., 2017). There is a wide array of promising formats, including multi-disciplinary educational headache programs (Patel et al., 2019; Nichols et al., 2019; Short, A. L., 2019; White et al., 2019), simple instructional online video or phone applications (Lagman-Bartolome et al., 2018; Thakur et al., 2018;), online behavioral training with psychologists or therapists (Penzien et al., 2015; Raggi et al., 2018; Sorbi et al., 2015; Sorbi et al., 2017), or exercise regimen and physical therapy (Kanji et al., 2015; Moore et al., 2017; Kroll et al., 2018). A few of the single-component therapies, such as physical therapy, have been and currently are part of standard headache treatment recommendations. However, there are less-publicized formats that may also appeal to patients, such as phone applications and relaxation training.

Barriers and Facilitators of Telemedicine

The unfreezing stage of Lewin's theory is based on acknowledging concerns to ease conflict that may arise in the subsequent change stage (Kaminski, 2011). The current literature on barriers and facilitators of telemedicine has only documented patient and provider perspectives. There were no studies that recorded office staff perceptions. The DNP project will take office staff opinions into account to increase their willingness to implement long-term change into the practice.

Patient Perspective

Friedman, Rajan, and Seidmann (2019) summarized patient comments regarding telemedicine interaction. Those in favor commended the access to care (especially to a preferred provider), decreased travel times and associated fees, minimal interruption to their work and other activities, shortened wait-times, no repetitive questions from staff, and feeling more comfortable in their environment of choice (Friedman et al., 2019). On the other hand, patient criticism included reports of experiencing technological anxiety, troubleshooting difficulties, inability to request a physical exam from the provider, feeling the visit was impersonal, and feeling self-conscious about revealing the state of their home (Friedman et al., 2019). Other studies also portrayed comparable patient opinions as well (Dorsey et al., 2018; Hatcher-Martin et al., 2019).

Provider Perspective

Healthcare providers shared similar praises regarding telemedicine, such as increasing patient access to their expertise, ease of using the technology, and minimal interruption in their workflow (Dorsey et al., 2018). Telecommunications is also a cost-effective delivery of care that does not require expensive buildings, space, and labor (Dorsey et al., 2018). Despite the advantages, Dorsey et al. (2018) acknowledged the presence of political, clinical, and social barriers. First, there has been a significant lack of reimbursement for telemedicine services (Dorsey et al., 2018; Hatcher-Martin et al., 2019). Dorsey et al. (2018) stated that payment models tend to support insurance-based guidelines rather than patient-centered care, and require impactful change directly at the legislative level. Second, provider competition may pose as a clinical barrier if patients prefer remote-accessed specialists over local clinicians (Dorsey et al., 2018). In this case, the authors suggested that local clinicians should adapt to the evolving

healthcare delivery systems and consider instituting telemedicine into their practice (Dorsey et al., 2018). Third, researchers recommend that healthcare providers recognize social barriers among vulnerable populations who lack technological capabilities or abilities, such as the elderly, those with chronic medical issues, those of low socioeconomic status, or reside in rural communities (Dorsey et al., 2018). Therefore, Dorsey et al. (2018) proposed offering telehealth services in patients' regular primary care clinic. In this case, the primary care physicians facilitate any necessary neurology consults simultaneously with the patient in the same visit. Understanding these limitations can help prepare practices to adequately address the issues as early as possible.

Summary and Quality of Evidence

According to Grove and Gray's levels of research evidence (2019), two papers were Level I systematic reviews, 11 papers were Level II RCTs, one paper was Level III quasi-experimental study, 10 papers were Level IV mixed-methods systematic reviews, and two papers were Level V cohort studies. A majority of the evidence on the topic of telemedicine was higher-level, yet, the self-management and self-care headache therapies were lower-level quality.

Although telemedicine is widely used in various specialties, headache disorders were underrepresented in the literature search. The majority of the studies found were conducted internationally where neurologists are rare and geographically dispersed. For example, the Norwegian studies extensively accumulated a large sample size that showed telemedicine was non-inferior to face-to-face visits and provided access to care for patients who would have driven hours for a headache treatment (Muller et al., 2016a, 2017a, 2017b, 2017c). However, because these patients only had one consult with the neurologist, headache disability could have been

further reduced if they were able to continue routine virtual visits with the neurologists instead of primary care.

On the other hand, the Americans designed their study to facilitate consistent oversight by neurologists, which not only increased access to care but also led to higher provider productivity (Rajan et al., 2017; Friedman et al., 2019). Unfortunately, due to the small sample size, the exclusion bias was substantial.

There were several headache screening algorithms and treatment protocols intended for clinicians. However, a telephone triage tool was not available for non-clinical staff. As a result, a simplified flowchart will be created that summarizes emergent versus urgent symptoms that can help the staff determine which patients are appropriate for telemedicine. While telemedicine is an extension of remote headache care for urgent concerns, there are numerous self-management and self-care options that patients can adopt as both preventative and rescue treatments. Therefore, one of the DNP project's objectives will be to compile a broader range of non-pharmacologic interventions that are available to patients.

Finally, seven quantitative studies on telemedicine for non-acute headache disorders showed strengths, such as reduced travel and related fees; and weaknesses, such as technical difficulties of telemedicine from an objective standpoint. The research also compared subjective qualitative data in the form of positive and negative comments from patients and providers. It is important to highlight that office staff input was not recorded in the literature. Consequently, the DNP project will take office staff participation and opinion into account to ensure successful guideline implementation.

Methods

Design

The author developed an evidence-based telemedicine guideline for primary headache patients in an outpatient neurology practice. The first objective assessed headache disability, lifestyle behaviors, and perception of telemedicine in recruited patients who are willing to try virtual visits. The second objective led to the development of an appointment algorithm based on best-available evidence for non-clinical staff to properly triage patients for telemedicine appointments. The third objective was to create a patient-centered educational handout about headaches and telemedicine, based on the survey responses.

Participants

The project included two samples, patients and staff members. Initially, the first objective was intended to recruit 20 patients. However, the COVID-19 pandemic decreased face-to-face visits and, therefore, caused difficulty recruiting patients. As a result, only a voluntary response sample of seven patients completed the surveys. They were diagnosed with primary headache disorders, which included migraines, tension, cluster, and medication-overuse headaches (ICD-10 codes G43, G44). The author applied the following inclusion and exclusion criteria. Patients were included if they were at least age 18 or older, patients of the clinic, diagnosed with a primary headache disorder or medication-overuse headache, confirmed ownership of or access to a computer or smartphone with high-speed internet, and proficient in English. For the second objective, three office staff members with scheduling responsibilities assisted in revising the appointment algorithm.

Setting

The project took place at an outpatient neurology practice in Southern California.

Ethical Considerations

CSULA IRB approved the project on August 12, 2020. Patients who fulfilled the inclusion criteria completed the surveys voluntarily and anonymously. The guideline development involved the participation of the office staff and neurologists.

Measures

First Objective: Patient Surveys

Demographics and clinical history measures were obtained using a 10-item, author-generated tool (Appendix B) based on the literature (Muller et al., 2017). It included six demographic questions, such as age, gender, education, occupation, employment status, and distance from the clinic. It also included four clinical items, such as the number of ED visits in the last year for headaches, the number of neurology office visits for headaches, frequency and type of pain medication or triptan use, and frequency and type of non-pharmacologic treatments. Participants filled in open-ended questions with their own answers.

Lifestyle behavior measures were obtained using a 12-item, author-generated tool (Appendix C) based on the literature (Hagen et al., 2018; Lund et al., 2019). Answers were formatted as a three-point Likert scale. It included questions about the patient's overall health status, sleep duration, and general stress level. The survey also inquired about how often they reported trouble falling or staying asleep, eating two to three meals daily, drinking water when thirsty, consuming caffeine, consuming alcohol, using tobacco, using other substances, turning to hobbies or activities to manage stress, and exercising per week. Participants circled one answer for each question.

Perceptions of telemedicine were obtained using a two item, author-generated tool (Appendix D) based on literature (Rajan et al., 2017). Answers were arranged on a three-point

Likert scale. It questioned the patients' likelihood of participating in telemedicine and their level of experience using computer or phone applications. Participants circled one answer for each question.

Procedures

First Objective: Recruitment of Headache Patients for Surveys

The author created and posted a study recruitment flyer (Appendix E) at the front reception and back office desks. The flyer encouraged any patients who suffered from headaches or migraines to request the survey packet. The flyer also listed the inclusion criteria and study investigators' contact information. Recruitment started on August 13, 2020. However, due to the lack of responses after two months, the author attached the flyer to new patient intake forms and end-of-visit summaries to increase recruitment potential. These new changes took place as of October 13, 2020.

Interested patients requested to fill out the study packet either from the receptionist or medical assistants. The study materials included the informational cover letter (Appendix F) and the three surveys. The completion of the surveys indicated their voluntary participation in the project, which were then returned into a locked drop-box at either desk. Because the author was absent during recruitment, the participants remained anonymous.

The first survey was received on December 2, 2020. An additional six surveys were collected in the following two months. On January 26, 2021, the author organized the data onto a spreadsheet. The analysis is elaborated further in the Methods of Analysis.

Second Objective: Development of the Appointment Algorithm and Schedule

The author reviewed available algorithms from the literature (Becker et al., 2015; Young et al., 2018), focusing on red flag symptoms that office staff can ask patients to immediately

assess and advise going to the ED if appropriate (Appendix G). The author listed the emergent symptoms and presented the first draft to the stakeholders on September 29, 2020. The neurologists recommended organizing the algorithm into a script and flowchart that the non-clinical staff can easily utilize. A second draft was presented and approved by the stakeholders on October 6, 2020.

On October 8, 2020, the author presented the appointment algorithm at the weekly staff meeting, which included the stakeholders and three office staff members. The group collectively discussed and understood that those patients who did not have red flag symptoms were eligible for a telemedicine appointment with a neurology provider. Feedback from all participants was integrated into the final algorithm (Appendix G).

In response to the COVID-19 pandemic, the office had previously implemented telemedicine capabilities and scheduling protocol as the new standard of care on April 1, 2020. This telemedicine schedule was programmed into the electronic practice management program. A 15 to 30-minute appointment slot was allowed from Monday to Friday during normal business hours of 9:00 am to 5:00 pm with any of the six neurology providers. Eligible telemedicine patients could then be scheduled with the next available provider.

Third Objective: Development of the Educational Material

The author reviewed the literature for three of the four sections of the handout, brief headache overview (Rizzoli & Mullaly, 2018), headache red flag symptoms that require immediate ED evaluation (Becker et al., 2015; Young et al., 2018), and introductory telemedicine information (Dorsey et al., 2018). The fourth and final section summarized clinic-specific recommendations based on the survey responses. The first draft was created on February

19, 2021, and presented to the stakeholders, other neurologists, and office staff on February 25, 2021 (Appendix H).

Method of Analysis

First Objective: Analyzing Survey Results

Data from the survey was imported into a spreadsheet for analysis (Appendices I, J, and K). Each patient was assigned a row and their answers were inputted into corresponding columns. From numeric data, the author calculated averages for age, distance from the clinic, number of ED visits in the past year, and number of neurology office visits in the past year. From open-ended answers, the author noted the most common responses. These responses included gender, highest level of education, occupation, and employment status. For two questions in which it was not possible to determine the average or the most common answer, the author calculated the number of participants who responded, which included the reported number of OTC or triptan doses per month and the number of non-pharmacological treatments of each per month.

Second and Third Objectives: Provider and Staff Feedback

Qualitative feedback was collected from the stakeholders, other neurologists, and the office staff members. The author recorded the minutes of the weekly meetings. The appropriate revisions were later incorporated into subsequent drafts of the appointment algorithm and the patient education handout.

Results

First Objective: Headache Patient Assessment Surveys

The first survey gathered demographics and clinical headache history which led to the following results (Appendix I). First, the average age and gender of the participants were 45 years old and female. Second, the patients worked diverse occupations, mostly full-time positions. Four participants reported high school as their highest level of education. Third, participants lived an average of 12.6 miles from the clinic. Fourth, two out of seven patients required ED visits in the past year due to headaches. This is in the setting of an average of 3.6 neurology office visits per year. And finally, six out of seven participants reported taking some kind of pharmacologic medication for headaches, three of which also utilized non-pharmacologic treatments.

The second survey measured lifestyle behaviors, which led to the following commonalities (Appendix J). First, most participants felt their overall health status was *good*. Second, a majority of patients slept less than five hours, in conjunction with reporting *sometimes* and *often* trouble sleeping. Third, most participants ate two to three meals per day and drank water when they felt thirsty. Fourth, a majority of patients *sometimes* drank caffeine and avoided alcohol, tobacco, and other substances. Fifth, despite reporting high-stress levels, most patients *sometimes* turn to stress-relieving hobbies. Finally, three participants exercised less than two days, while three participants exercised more than five days per week.

The third survey collected patient perceptions of telemedicine, which resulted in the following interpretations (Appendix K): most participants were *very likely* to partake in telemedicine, most patients identified with having *plenty* of experience with computers or phone applications.

Second Objective: Appointment Algorithm

The author surmised similarities in the assessment of red flag headache symptoms. High-risk patients may report having fever or chills, sudden onset, change in their level of consciousness, neurological symptoms, feeling progressively worse or different from previous headaches, or were at least 50 years of age (Becker et al., 2015; Young et al., 2018). Upon reviewing the checklist, the stakeholders advised simplifying medical terminology for non-clinical staff members and patients. For example, asking if patients had any neurological symptoms was clarified to ask for specifics, such as numbness, tingling, or weakness. The general statement asking if the patient had any change in their level of consciousness was replaced by asking if they felt confused. Also, the stakeholders felt that a checklist may not be adequate and recommended a flowchart design that was straightforward to navigate. Lastly, a neurologist highlighted that severe headaches were commonly described as *the worst headache in my life*, and should be a checklist item as well.

When the second draft of the appointment algorithm was presented at the weekly staff meeting, the three staff members commented that the algorithm was easy to follow. However, all three staff members agreed that asking the patient seven questions while the patient is suffering from a headache seemed too much. They were also apprehensive about how they would convince the patient to seek immediate help as a non-clinical employee. One of the medical assistants mentioned that most patients would demand to speak to their provider immediately or expect someone to call them back as soon as possible. The stakeholders and neurologists agreed that seven questions may seem like a lot, but felt all were necessary to recognize early signs and symptoms of a possible life-threatening medical emergency. At the end of the meeting, the office

staff members agreed on a trial run of the appointment algorithm for two weeks and would review the results at the following staff meeting.

Third Objective: Educational Material

The patient-centered, self-care recommendations of the educational handout were derived from the surveys (Appendices I, J, and K). First, the two patients who reported visiting the ED in the past year for headaches had also reported fewer neurology office visits and a relatively high use of triptan or pain medication. This indicated the importance of maintaining close neurology follow-ups to adjust their treatment plan and avoid medication overuse. Second, a minority of those surveyed had a non-pharmacologic intervention in place. As a result, the author noted various modalities from the literature, such as physical therapy, acupuncture, biofeedback, relaxation training, and phone applications. Third, most participants complained of poor sleep, which prompted the discussion of sleep hygiene as a crucial self-care habit. Lastly, a majority of the patients reported high-stress levels, and yet, had hobbies in place only *sometimes*. Therefore, the author emphasized the therapeutic effects of leisure activities to relieve stress.

At the staff meeting, the first draft of the education handout was generally well-received. Mutual supportive comments mentioned that it was helpful to list emergency symptoms and basic telemedicine facts. The providers felt that the recommendations based on the surveys were insightful pointing out that sleep deprivation was a major headache trigger, and that most patients did not have a non-pharmacologic intervention in place. It was also recommended that the clinic's name and contact information be included on the patient education handout so patients are able to call the office if needed.

Key Facilitators and Barriers

The DNP project was executed during the COVID-19 pandemic, which created unintended facilitators and barriers for the project. The barrier for the first objective was presented when the Governor of California issued an executive order to shelter-at-home starting on March 19, 2020 (Executive Department State of California, 2020). This led to the cancellation of all appointments. However, this also served as a facilitator by favorably accelerating plans for telemedicine implementation. Due to the new protocol, the clinic patients seemed more willing to participate in telemedicine, as indicated in their survey responses. The pandemic also served as a deterrent to study recruitment by substantially decreasing office foot traffic, which consequently lowered the visibility of the desk flyers. Despite the clinic's gradual resumption of in-office appointments in August 2020, and the attachment of recruitment flyers to intake forms and after-visit summaries, the recruitment pace was slow. When the author interviewed the office staff members, the two medical assistants noted two sources of delay, themselves and the patients. The medical assistants admitted that they were not always consistent with attaching the flyer to the patient forms because of non-stop office telephone calls. They also acknowledged rooming the patient as quickly as possible for fear of possible COVID-19 exposure, despite wearing appropriate personal protective equipment (PPE). Furthermore, the medical assistants stated patients seemed uninterested, overwhelmed, or said they would take it home and bring it back with their next visit. Therefore, only seven participants volunteered instead of the initial goal of twenty.

Developing the appointment algorithm for the second objective was productive among the stakeholders, other neurologists, and the staff members. The initial literacy barriers were addressed by simplifying the medical terminology into a language that most patients would be

able to understand. However, the medical assistants anticipated additional barriers once the appointment algorithm was ready for a trial run, which may stem from frustrations among those in the front office attempting to use the new telemedicine guideline when the patient refused to comply with the final recommendation. These barriers will be further assessed after the conclusion of the DNP project.

Developing the patient educational material was facilitated by data from the previous objectives. For example, the literature review contributed to the brief headache facts, red flag headache symptoms, and telemedicine basics. The third objective drew attention to common unhealthy habits that could be improved independently if properly advised. The author encountered a design challenge, specifically presenting pertinent information in a way that is not crowded with information.

Discussion

Recommendations Within the Neurology Clinic

The application of Kurt Lewin's Change Theory was appropriate for this DNP project, especially in the setting of the COVID-19 pandemic. First, in the unfreezing phase, telemedicine was undisputedly pursued to continue providing care to patients sheltering at home. The stakeholders, neurologists, and office staff members readily awaited telemedicine to launch. Second, although the providers seamlessly adapted to telemedicine, the changing phase was met with the most resistance when presenting the patient surveys and the appointment algorithm to the office staff members. This is the current phase of the DNP project. As the in-person foot traffic increased, the patient surveys were more of an afterthought while trying to room the patient safely according to social-distancing and PPE protocols. Furthermore, although the non-clinical staff is adept at scheduling telemedicine appointments, the headache algorithm posed a threat at slowing down their workflow. The staff also stated a valid point that the clinic patients tend to demand individual attention and only trust recommendations from their medical providers. Third and lastly, the refreezing phase is a future stage in which the practice can continue beyond the allowable timeframe of the DNP project to pilot the algorithm.

The following recommendations may be helpful on increasing buy-in from the office staff members and the patients at the change stage. First, recruiting other change agents from the start, such as other neurologists and the office manager, can empower the staff more effectively to distribute surveys. Second, an inexpensive incentive for patients filling out the surveys may boost recruitment, such as a keychain hand sanitizer. Third, even if baked goods were provided at staff meetings, it is more impactful to verbally recognize an early adopter of change through immediate praise and formal comment to the office manager regarding their job performance.

Future Implications for the Guideline

The DNP project developed a guideline for triaging headache patients for telemedicine, assessing whether the patients would be receptive to telemedicine, and creating an educational headache handout based on survey responses. In addition, the project was unique from studies in the literature review by recognizing office staff feedback as contributions to the evolution of telemedicine. Their buy-in, and ultimately their ongoing participation, is critical in the changing and refreezing phase of the framework.

In contrast, developing the guideline specific to this outpatient neurology clinic during a pandemic also gave rise to weaknesses. For example, the small sample size only allowed for average calculations and commonalities. If the recruitment took place pre-pandemic or given additional time, it may have been possible to collect a larger sample that more accurately represents the clinic's patient population. Likewise, this project's findings are not generalizable to other practices due to the small sample size. However, outpatient settings such as primary care practices may benefit from surveying their patients to determine knowledge gaps of other illnesses that can benefit from telemedicine and tailored patient education. Finally, although the guideline development is currently in the change phase, it is an ongoing work-in-progress aimed at increasing the front office staff's confidence in utilizing the headache algorithm and improving access to care for headache patients by using telemedicine appointments.

In conclusion, plans for a staff in-service to review and finally test the algorithm, improve access to care for headache patients via telemedicine, as well as the distribution of the patient handout will allow this author to gather more data, which will further extend the benefits of this DNP project.

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Appendix A

Kurt Lewin's Change Theory

Appendix B

Survey 1 Clinical History and Demographics

Survey #1: Clinical history and demographics

	Instructions: Fill in your answers below.
1 Age:	
2 Gender:	
3 Highest level of education:	
4 Occupation:	
5 Employment status:	
6 Distance from clinic or zip code of home address:	
7 How many emergency department visits were for headaches in the last year?	
8 How many neurology office visits were for headaches in the past year?	
9 On average in a month, how many doses of triptan or over-the-counter pain medication, on average, do you take for headache?	
10 On average in a month, how many times do you need to use non-pharmacologic treatments (such as acupuncture, physical therapy, massage therapy, cold compresses, etc.)?	

Appendix C

Survey 2 Lifestyle Behaviors

Survey #2: Lifestyle Behaviors

Instructions: Circle one answer for each question below.

1	Overall health status	Good	Average	Poor
2	How many of hours do you typically sleep?	Less than 5 hours	6-9 hours	More than 10 hours
3	Do you typically have trouble either falling asleep or staying asleep?	Never	Sometimes	Often
4	Do you typically eat 2-3 meals per day?	Never	Sometimes	Often
5	Do you typically drink water when you are thirsty?	Never	Sometimes	Often
6	Do you consume caffeinated beverages (coffee, tea, energy drinks, etc.)?	Never	Sometimes	Often
7	Do you consume alcoholic beverages (beer, spirits, cocktails, etc.)?	Never	Sometimes	Often
8	Do you use tobacco products (cigarettes, cigars, vapors, etc.)?	Never	Sometimes	Often
9	Do you use other substances (marijuana, etc.)?	Never	Sometimes	Often
10	How would you rate your overall stress level?	Mild	Moderate	High
11	Do you have activities or hobbies in place that helps to manage stress?	Never	Sometimes	Often
12	How many days per week do you exercise?	0-2 days	3-4 days	5 or more days

Appendix D

Survey 3 Perceptions of Telemedicine

Survey #3: Perceptions of Technology

Participant # _____	Instructions: Circle one answer for each question below.		
1 What is the likelihood that you would like to participate in telemedicine?	Not Likely	Likely	Very Likely
2 What is your level of experience in using computer or phone applications?	No Experience	Little to Some Experience	Plenty of Experience

Appendix E

Study Recruitment Flyer

Do you suffer from **headaches** or **migraines**?

Please ask to complete a brief survey!
(about 5 minutes)

To Participate You Must Be:

- 18+ years old
- A patient of this clinic
- Diagnosed with migraines, tension, cluster, or medication-overuse headaches
- Have internet and computer/smartphone access
- Have basic skills to use a computer/smartphone

To Learn More, Contact:

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THIS PROJECT HAS BEEN REVIEWED BY THE CALIFORNIA STATE UNIVERSITY, LOS ANGELES INSTITUTIONAL REVIEW BOARD FOR THE PROTECTION OF HUMAN SUBJECTS IN RESEARCH. ADDITIONAL CONCERNS AND COMPLAINTS, OR QUESTIONS REGARDING YOUR RIGHTS AS A RESEARCH PARTICIPANT, SHOULD BE DIRECTED TO THE ASSOCIATE VICE PRESIDENT FOR RESEARCH (Phone number: 323-343-5368).

Appendix F

Study Informational Letter

INFORMATIONAL COVER LETTER

Guideline Development to Implement Telemedicine for Headache Patients in an Outpatient Clinic

To Project Participant:

You are invited to take part in a research project conducted by a doctoral student at California State University, Los Angeles under the supervision of Dr. Jean O'Neil. In this study, we hope to learn more about patients with primary headaches and develop a guideline that will help implement telemedicine efficiently and effectively at our clinic. You are an ideal participant of this study if you suffer from headaches, including migraines, tension, cluster, and medication-overuse. We hope that our research will lead to better management of patients with headaches via the use of telemedicine. You must be at least 18 years old to participate.

If you agree to participate in this study you may complete three paper surveys at any office visit. The paper surveys are voluntary and will be kept anonymous. The surveys will inquire about clinical headache history, lifestyle behaviors, and perceptions of technology. It will take about 10-15 minutes to complete, providing written short answers to open-ended questions and circling the most suitable response. The surveys will then be dropped in a slotted, locked-box before leaving the clinic. Turning in the survey concludes your participation in the study. The initial part of this project is to develop a guideline and pilot a program with the front desk staff to ensure they are comfortable and competent to book patients with headaches into telemedicine appointments. I will also be developing an educational tool on headache self-management based on data we will be getting from the first 20 patients willing to enroll in this study.

There are minimal risks to this study. Your participation is voluntary, and may withdraw at any time with no consequence or penalty. There is no compensation for your participation. There will be little to no public presentation or publication risks when study results are published in a paper and presented to the faculty and cohort. As a safeguard, data will be reported by number or in aggregate form.

Reports resulting from this study will not identify you as a participant. All information gathered in this study will remain confidential and be given out only with your permission or as required by law. If you give us permission by voluntarily completing the surveys, we will protect your confidentiality. However, like teachers and health care workers, we are obligated under California law to report any abuse that we encounter or reasonably suspect. The principal investigator, Dr. Jean O'Neil, will keep the data for 3 years in a locked drawer at CSULA Simpson Tower Rm 404. There will be no audio or video recording involved.

In all cases, in the event of a need for emergency care, you will be with a provider, however, if needed 911 will be called. Any and all incurred health care costs associated with participation in this research project are still the responsibility of the subject, patient, or participant.

If you have any questions about this research at any time, please call Jean O'Neil, DNP, FNP-BC at [redacted], or write her at joneil3@calstatela.edu. You can also contact the co-investigator and neurology provider, Kasalyn Thuvamontolrat at [redacted], or write her at kthuvamon@csu.fullerton.edu.

THIS PROJECT HAS BEEN REVIEWED BY THE CALIFORNIA STATE UNIVERSITY, LOS ANGELES INSTITUTIONAL REVIEW BOARD FOR THE PROTECTION OF HUMAN SUBJECTS IN RESEARCH. ADDITIONAL CONCERNS AND COMPLAINTS, OR QUESTIONS REGARDING YOUR RIGHTS AS A RESEARCH PARTICIPANT, SHOULD BE DIRECTED TO THE ASSOCIATE VICE PRESIDENT FOR RESEARCH (Phone number: 323-343-5368).

Effective January 2018

Appendix G

Headache Appointment Algorithm

- If you are not sure, ask a neurology provider in the office.
- If the patient insists on speaking to a neurology provider, state that this is a new triage protocol approved by the neurologists to prevent delay in care.

Appendix H

Patient Educational Handout

A Helpful Handout for Those with Headaches

What are headaches/migraines?

- Caused by physical pressure/tension, inflammation, or irritation of other structures in or surrounding the head

How are they treated?

- Changing unhealthy habits, taking over-the-counter vitamins/pain medications/prescribed medications, and/or using complementary therapies

If you answer yes to ANY of the following during “the worst headache of your life”, **CALL 911 IMMEDIATELY:**

- 50 years old or older?
- Fever or chills?
- Sudden onset?
- Feel confused?
- Numbness, tingling, and/or weakness?
- Progressively worse over days or weeks?
- Different from previous headaches?

What is telemedicine?

- Using technology to provide clinical care to patients from any location – even home

Who can use telemedicine?

- Anyone with a computer/mobile device, internet connection, and some experience in using technology

When is telemedicine appropriate for headaches?

- If headaches do NOT possess ANY of the above symptoms that require 911 attention
- Schedule a telemedicine appointment and complete a visit with your neurology provider... without leaving home!

Headache Treatment Recommendations:

- Visit your neurology provider every 3 months if headaches are not under adequate control
- Taking “as needed” medications more than recommended (such as “triptans”, acetaminophen, ibuprofen, naproxen, aspirin) can lead to medication overuse, or rebound, headaches
- Complementary therapies include physical therapy, acupuncture, biofeedback, relaxation training, and phone apps (such as Migraine Buddy, Migraine Monitor, and Relax Lite)
- Sleep hygiene is commonly overlooked. This means going to bed at the same time every night, making sure your bedroom is dark and quiet, removing electronics (TVs, tablets, phones) from the bedroom, avoiding large meals and caffeine before bedtime, and exercising during the day.
- Turning to hobbies can relieve stress. This can include yoga, hiking, journaling, spending time with family/friends/pet, and many more!

Appendix I

Survey 1 Clinical History and Demographics Data

Patient	Age	Gender	Highest level of education	Occupation	Employment status	Distance from clinic (miles)	Number of ED visits for headaches in the past year	Number of neuro office visits for headaches in the past year	Average number of triptan or OTC pain medication doses taken in a month	Average number of times non-pharmacologic treatments used in a month
1	67	F	4 year college	Artist	Self-employed	43	0	4	6	10
2	44	F	High school	Merch stocker	Full time	3	0	7	Every once in a while	0
3	48	F	Master's	Technical specialist	Full time	18	0	2	0	0
4	44	F	Some college	EMT	Full time	5	0	6	30	0
5	54	M	High school	Gardener	Full time	5	2	2	Almost daily	Not often
6	23	F	High school	Fast food clerk	Full time	3	2	3	12	0
7	35	F	High school	(left unanswered)	(left unanswered)	11	0	1	10	8
AVERAGE or MOST COMMON ANSWER	45	F	High school	(Average and most common not applicable)	Full time	12.6	0.6	3.6	(Average not applicable, but 6 out of 7 patients reported taking some kind of medication)	(Average not applicable, but 3 out of 7 patients reported using some kind of treatment)

Appendix J

Survey 2 Lifestyle Behaviors Data

Patient	Overall health	Hours of sleep per night	Trouble sleeping	Eat 2-3 meals per day	Drink water when thirsty	Caffeine	Alcohol	Tobacco	Other substances	Stress level	Activities or hobbies to manage stress	Days per week of exercise
1	Good	Less than 5 hours	Often	Often	Often	Often	Never	Never	Never	High	Often	5 or more days
2	Good	Less than 5 hours	Never	Sometimes	Often	Sometimes	Sometimes	Never	Sometimes	Moderate	Never	0-2 days
3	Average	6-9 hours	Sometimes	Often	Sometimes	Sometimes	Sometimes	Never	Never	Moderate	Sometimes	0-2 days
4	Good	6-9 hours	Often	Often	Often	Never	Never	Often	Never	Moderate	Sometimes	5 or more days
5	Average	Less than 5 hours	Sometimes	Often	Often	Sometimes	Sometimes	Never	Never	High	Sometimes	0-2 days
6	Poor	Less than 5 hours	Sometimes	Often	Often	Sometimes	Never	Never	Never	High	Sometimes	3-4 days
7	Good	Less than 5 hours	Often	Often	Often	Sometimes	Never	Never	Never	High	Often	5 or more days
MOST COMMON ANSWER	Good	Less than 5 hours	Sometimes AND Often	Often	Often	Sometimes	Never	Never	Never	High	Sometimes	0-2 days AND 5 or more days

Appendix K

Survey 3 Perceptions of Telemedicine Data

Patient	Likelihood of participating in telemedicine	Level of experience with computer or phone apps
1	Very likely	Plenty
2	Not likely	Little to Some
3	Very likely	Plenty
4	Very likely	Little to Some
5	Likely	Little to Some
6	Very likely	Plenty
7	Likely	Plenty
MOST COMMON ANSWER		
	Very Likely	Plenty